

ANALYSIS OF THE SITUATION AND PROBLEMS OF TEACHING RUSSIAN TO TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY STUDENTS AND THE USE OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGIES IN DEVELOPING AN ELECTRONIC TEXTBOOK

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Abstract. *The use of various innovative methods in lessons facilitates the mastery of Russian writing, while the application of electronic textbooks in the educational process promotes the formation of research, exploratory, and independent activities. The development of interest in scientific and educational-methodological activities can occur through the lens of continuous improvement of the teacher's methodological competence.*

Keywords: *Electronic textbook, activity, manual, problem, education, formation, international communication, theory, pedagogical education.*

АНАЛИЗ СОСТОЯНИЯ И ПРОБЛЕМ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА СТУДЕНТАМ ТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ ВУЗОВ И ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ КОМПЬЮТЕРНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ПРИ РАЗРАБОТКЕ ЭЛЕКТРОННОГО УЧЕБНИКА

Аннотация. *Использование на уроках различных инновационных методов способствует овладению русской письменной речью, а применение электронных учебников в учебном процессе способствует формированию исследовательской, поисковой и самостоятельной деятельности. Развитие интереса к научной и учебно-методической деятельности может происходить через призму постоянного совершенствования методической компетентности учителя.*

Ключевые слова: *Электронный учебник, деятельность, пособие, проблема, образование, формирование, международное общение, теория, педагогическое образование.*

Innovative education in the modern world is a prerequisite for the theoretical rethinking of educational practices and finding solutions through the development of modern methodologies and theories of pedagogical education. A prime example is the Russian language, which has become a language of international communication. More and more people feel the need to communicate competently, understand, process, and transmit information in a non-native language.

It is also important to note that due to Uzbekistan's transition from Cyrillic to Latin script, students face significant challenges in mastering Russian grammar. Therefore, the use of various innovative methods in lessons facilitates the mastery of Russian writing, while the application of electronic textbooks in the educational process promotes the formation of research, exploratory, and independent activities. [1, pp. 125-127]

The structure of the electronic textbook is as follows:

- Theoretical section;
- Independent practical exercises;
- Testing;
- Reference section;
- Literature;
- Glossary. [2, pp. 274-280]

The "Test Tasks" section includes tests for all chapters. The tests consist of various types of tasks: simple selection (one correct answer out of 4-6 options) and complex selection (two or three correct answers out of 6-10 options).

Control questions are provided after each topic. Additionally, there are tasks of two levels for independent problem-solving. [3, pp. 387-390]

Due to the aforementioned problems and shortcomings, graduates entering the field of technical education face difficulties at the beginning of their careers. Firstly, there is the constant need for self-improvement to develop their skills and achieve the necessary level of expertise. Secondly, this situation requires specialists with underdeveloped communication skills to reach a high level of mastery and readiness for innovative activities.

To identify factors for the continuous development of the methodological competence of Russian language teachers, a comparative analysis of undergraduate curricula is conducted. This is relevant due to the following circumstances:

- In the context of educational pluralism, it is necessary for Russian language teachers to learn modern scientific and pedagogical approaches and the ability to independently solve methodological tasks in their daily pedagogical activities;
- The development of interest in scientific and educational-methodological activities can occur through the lens of continuous improvement of the teacher's methodological competence.

The choice of methods for teaching Russian in the pedagogical process is one of the most important issues.

Thus, professional concepts in Russian include techniques or technological processes in a specific field of development, the work of future specialists in a particular area, as well as the knowledge that forms the basis of professional skills and competencies. [4, pp. 141-154]

Media education pursues two equal goals: the development of an integrative approach to media texts and the enhancement of students' communicative, professional, and creative abilities, i.e., the ability to receive, create, and transmit media texts. "Media communication skills (competence, awareness) involve the ability to perceive, create, and transmit messages through technical and semiotic systems, considering their limitations. [5] It is based on a professional-critical approach and the ability to engage in media communications with others based on their professional knowledge."

Improving the information skills of future engineers for industrial activities in Russian, based on media technologies in higher technical educational institutions, is an important factor in preparing them for technical professional activities and enhancing the quality of Russian language teaching methods.

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